

Digital Twin for Datacenter: HPC4AI UniTO Case Study

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Abstract. The HPC4AI (High-Performance Computing for Artificial Intelligence) datacenter at the University of Turin's Computer Science Department was established to meet the rapidly growing computational demands of interdisciplinary AI research. HPC4AI innovates by redefining the traditional roles of Cloud and High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems, where the Cloud provides a modern interface for HPC, and HPC acts as an accelerator for Cloud applications. To date, it has supported over 40 research projects spanning diverse fields such as astronomy, medicine, and human sciences. Additionally, HPC4AI serves as a research and development platform for exploring, developing, and testing novel datacenter technologies. It features a variety of experimental computing platforms and the first prototype of a two-phase evaporative server cooling system. This work outlines the operational management of HPC4AI, highlighting challenges, lessons learned, and key opportunities related to digital twins for datacenters.

Keywords: HPC4AI · Datacenter · Digital Twin · Artificial Intelligence · High Performance Computing (HPC) · Energy modeling

1 Introduction

The HPC4AI datacenter was established to meet the evolving computational demands of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications by rethinking the conventional separation between Cloud and HPC systems [1]. Rather than treating them as distinct paradigms, HPC4AI integrates Cloud and HPC into a symbiotic system, in which the Cloud provides flexible, on-demand services, such as model inferences (e.g., the PRAISE cardiopathic risk score) via virtual machines and containers. Meanwhile, compute intensive tasks like model training are delegated to the HPC clusters as batch jobs. This architecture enables the Cloud to serve as a modern, user-friendly interface for HPC, while HPC accelerates performance-critical components of Cloud applications. A practical illustration of this integration is represented by the Jupyter Workflow. Jupyter notebooks offer a feature-rich, cell-based web interface that seamlessly integrates code snippets with descriptive

metadata [2, 3], facilitating remote execution and making them popular among domain experts and AI practitioners. Unlike traditional Jupyter notebooks, which execute code cells sequentially on a single server, Jupyter Workflow enables users to orchestrate complex workflows and execute them across heterogeneous hybrid HPC-Cloud infrastructures. In this configuration, the Cloud hosts the web-based frontend, while distributed execution is coordinated and offloaded to the HPC backend. This model supports scalability, reproducibility, and resource optimisation, and aligns with emerging concepts of Digital Twins (DTs) and scientific workflows in AI-driven research environments [5, 7, 12]. Indeed, DTs represent a transformative innovation for data center management, enabling real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and energy optimization. By virtually replicating physical infrastructure, DTs support rapid intervention in case of anomalies, can improve system resilience and reduce environmental impact, key features to shift toward more efficient and sustainable HPC environments. Their integration with IoT and AI further enhances dynamic system control, supporting predictive analytics and adaptive cooling strategies [6, 8, 9].

HPC4AI operates as a federated competence center with two main hubs: one located at the University of Turin's Computer Science Department and the other at Politecnico di Torino. The remainder of this paper focuses specifically on the University of Turin (UNITO) hub (Fig. 1), which serves as a case study for exploring challenges, current gaps and opportunities in the development of DTs for datacenters.

Fig. 1. HPC4AI@UNITO datacenter

2 Design of HPC4AI at the Computer Science Department, UNITO

HPC4AI is hosted in a custom-designed 250 kVA data center located at the University of Turin's Computer Science Department. The facility is engineered to meet Tier-III availability standards, ensuring an uptime of 99.982%, equivalent to no more than 1.6

h of annual downtime [7]. Redundant power and cooling systems guarantee continuous operation. In the event of short power interruptions, two UPS units temporarily power the IT equipment until a diesel generator can restore power to both IT and cooling systems. Over four years of operation, the datacenter experienced only one downtime, necessitated by the connection of a second chiller to the UPS-protected power supply.

Power Distribution: Power is distributed through ceiling-mounted crossbars, allowing for maximum flexibility in connecting rack PDUs. The datacenter comprises 16 racks, each equipped with two PDUs that monitor load at the phase level. Servers are connected to balance the load across the three phases, while the Building Management System (BMS) continuously monitors power at the distribution transformer for real-time Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) monitoring.

Cooling System: The datacenter employs a cold-hot aisle design, with the hot aisle centrally located and eight racks on either side, topped by an extractor hood. Cold air is supplied from above, leveraging natural air circulation to reduce fan energy consumption. Two adiabatic chillers on the roof operate in three modes: free cooling, evaporation, or compression, depending on weather conditions. These chillers primarily function in free or evaporative modes, enhancing energy efficiency due to their strategic location in a windy area with dry air from surrounding mountains. Water consumption is notably low, with only 1671 cubic meters used over four years, equivalent to just 5.35 times the average per capita water consumption in Italy (based on 2021 data) [4].

Showroom and Educational Value: Glass walls on two sides of the server room provide students and visitors with a clear view, significantly enhancing the educational value of the datacenter. A challenge was soundproofing the facility, given its proximity to departmental offices. The use of triple glazing reduced noise levels by up to 92 dB, effectively silencing high-speed cooling fans. Additionally, cooling pipes on the exterior were constructed from specialized soundproofing materials to minimize noise pollution both inside and outside the facility.

2.1 A Multitenant Cloud

The OpenStack-based cloud system features a robust infrastructure, comprising over 2400 physical cores, 60 TB of RAM, and 120 GPUs spanning three generations (NVIDIA T4, V100, and A40). The system is interconnected via a high-speed 25 Gb/s network and offers four distinct storage classes, each with unique characteristics and cost structures. These storage options range from ultra-fast Ceph storage utilizing nVMe disks (40 TB) to fast SSD storage based on Dell EMC Unity (1 PB) and extend to spinning disk-based storage for cold data (1 PB), which is backed up using Dell EMC Avamar (1 PB). Additionally, a smaller 4-node system replicates the cloud infrastructure for testing and research purposes. Users can request virtual machines (VMs) and utilize UNITO's custom management tools to deploy private, secure, and elastic instances of Kubernetes. These Kubernetes instances are enhanced with single sign-on capabilities through Keycloak, providing robust identity and access management features.

Fig. 2. HPC4AI BMS system overview and data display.

2.2 Modular HPC System

The HPC cluster comprises heterogeneous compute nodes:

- 68 Intel nodes (2x Xeon CPU E5–2697 v4, 36 cores with HT disabled, 128 GB RAM, OmniPath 100 Gb/s)
- 4 Arm nodes (Ampere Altra 80 cores, 512 GB RAM, 2xA100 GPUs, 2xBlueField2 DPUs, Ethernet 100 Gb/s)
- 4 Intel nodes (2x Xeon Gold 6230, 40 cores with HT disabled, 1 TB RAM, 1xT4 + 1xV100 GPUs, Ethernet 100 Gb/s)
- 4 Nvidia nodes (1x Grace CPU, 72 cores, 573 GB RAM, 1xH100 GPU, Ethernet 100 Gb/s) network.

These are supported by 2 all-flash HPC storage systems: BeeGFS hosting user homes (50 TB) and LUSTRE as scratch partition (20 TB). The system is managed by UrgentSLURM, a self-developed SLURM extension that manages the booking of nodes via a web calendar.

2.3 Experimental System

HPC4AI serves as a platform for hosting experimental and prototype architecture, including:

- SiFive and Milk-V RISC-V servers,
- Esperanto RISC-V boards
- NVIDIA development kits equipped with Bluefield DPUs

These systems support cutting-edge research in innovative computing architectures. Notably, HPC4AI is home to the first commercial prototype of a two-phase evaporative cooling system designed for high-power density GPU-enabled servers.

This prototype features a dual-socket Intel Xeon Platinum 8458P configuration paired with four NVIDIA H100 SXM2 GPUs. The evaporator is engineered to dissipate up to 1000 W per socket, handling thermal densities exceeding 70 W/cm². Two-phase cooling is anticipated to surpass the efficiency of current liquid cooling solutions, offering

additional benefits such as the use of dielectric (environmentally friendly and non-toxic) gas. This design mitigates the risks associated with liquid cooling, such as damage from pipe ruptures. Furthermore, the system utilizes thin, low-pressure pipes, reducing costs and enhancing overall efficiency by leveraging evaporation for heat dissipation.

3 Monitoring System for the Digital Infrastructure

Comprehensive monitoring is essential for ensuring smooth operation and effective management of the HPC4AI datacenter. To achieve this, three overarching monitoring systems are employed, each targeting different aspects of data center operations: one focused on DC servers, another integrated into the Building Management System (BMS), and a standalone system uploading data to the cloud with complementary sensors.

Power and Cooling: The Vertiv Critical Insight BMS plays a crucial role in controlling and monitoring the status of power distribution and cooling equipment. The main dashboard provides a concise summary of the system's health status (Fig. 2). In the event of anomalies or faults, alarms are triggered to facilitate prompt interventions. For power management, the system tracks energy efficiency to identify opportunities for improvement, using sensors from the distribution transformer down to the PDUs in the racks. For cooling, it monitors air temperature and humidity at both the chiller and rack levels, ensuring balanced cooling and preventing hot spots. Additionally, it surveils the dew point to prevent damage from water condensation on IT equipment.

Air Quality: To ensure the longevity of IT equipment, monitoring extends beyond temperature and humidity to include various particulate matter in the air. Three LaCentralina air quality monitoring stations [5] are used to track pollutants such as particle matters of different sizes (PM1, PM2.5, PM4, and PM10) and gases (CO₂, tVOC, O₃, NH₃, CO, NO₂, and CH₂O). Particulate matter can be detrimental to IT equipment by depositing dust on components, potentially clogging airflows and fans.

IT Systems: The operational health of all IT subsystems, OpenStack, SLURM, Ceph, and Unity, is monitored through their respective dashboards. In addition, the Pandora FMS monitoring platform is employed to track real-time resource usage (CPU, RAM) and to detect potential performance bottlenecks across the infrastructure.

Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) [6]: Based on monitored metrics, particular attention is given to tracking the Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) of the data center. PUE quantifies how efficiently a data center uses energy by comparing IT equipment energy usage to total energy consumption. A PUE value closer to 1 indicates ideal operational efficiency, where most energy is used for IT resources rather than cooling or other purposes. The recent historical record of energy consumption and the achieved shows a PUE of 1.1, notably lower than the estimated global average PUE of 1.56 for data centers [6, 12].

4 Datacenter Modeling for Digital Twin

The data coming from the sensors and the information related to the data center are converging in a BIM model that will be used as a basis for the DT of the HPC4AI in the modelling phase [7, 11] and later as a support to visualize the data (Fig. 3). The BIM model was based on CAD files and used for building energy modeling.

Fig. 3. Model creation to simulate and visualize the DC indoor conditions and create the DT

The primary objective of developing a DT for the data center is to consolidate critical operational data and system insights into a virtual replica, enabling real-time lifecycle management and dynamic performance simulations. DTs represent a transformative paradigm in infrastructure management by supporting predictive maintenance, anomaly detection, and scenario-based optimization of both energy use and equipment operation [9, 12]. When integrated with IoT sensor networks, AI-driven analytics, and BIM, DTs provide a robust framework for simulating thermal and electrical behavior, assessing system resilience, and improving power usage effectiveness (PUE) [11]. BIM accelerates DT deployment by supplying precise spatial and semantic modeling of architectural and mechanical systems, and enhances the DT's reliability in energy optimization, fault detection, and long-term sustainability planning [8–11].

The DT for the HPC4AI data center is being developed to progressively incorporate these capabilities with the goal of enhancing energy efficiency and operational reliability in high-performance computing environments. The initial phase focused on constructing a validated, simulation-ready model to evaluate energy performance, indoor environmental quality, and thermal exchanges between the data center and its host facility under various operational conditions. This foundational model supports the integration of future DT features such as real-time monitoring, data-driven control strategies, and adaptive system optimization. Key priorities include managing internal heat generation, maintaining optimal environmental parameters for computing equipment, and minimizing energy losses through efficient heat dissipation. A dynamic simulation model has been established as a preliminary implementation, structured around the detailed configuration of system parameters and the evolving DT framework.

Modeling Approach: Dynamic simulations were conducted using IES Virtual Environment (IES VE), a leading building performance simulation platform (Fig. 4).

Climate Data Integration: Local environmental conditions critically influence free and evaporative cooling efficiency. Climate files integrated into the simulation software were selected based on the site's geographic location. These files provide granular datasets, including outdoor temperature, relative humidity, wind speed/direction, and solar radiation, ensuring accurate representation of regional climate patterns and reliable energy performance assessments.

Thermal Zone Definition: Geometric modeling formed the foundation for accurately replicating the data center's layout, ensuring fidelity in representing spatial configurations, components, and thermal zone interactions. The model was cross verified against

technical drawings and physical measurements to ensure dimensional accuracy, volumetric consistency, and zone adjacency relationships. Four distinct thermal zones were defined: the server room, cold aisle, hot aisle, and supply/return air plenums.

The process encompassed rigorous validation of geometric parameters, thermal zone boundaries, and system interactions to align the digital model with real-world operational dynamics.

4.1 Geometric Modeling

Thermal zones within the data center were delineated based on their specific functions to ensure precise control over airflow and thermal conditions. The zones were categorized into primary, auxiliary, and adjacent spaces.

Primary Spaces: *Server Room/Cold Aisle:* This area is responsible for distributing cooled air to racks via strategically placed supply grilles. *Hot Aisle:* An isolated area where hot air from racks accumulates, designed for efficient air recovery through the return plenum. *Supply and Return Plenums:* Elevated spaces facilitating cooled air distribution and hot air recovery.

Auxiliary Spaces: *Control Room:* Dedicated for monitoring and managing operations. *Water Treatment Room:* Supports evaporative cooling systems. *Q.E. and UPS Room:* Houses electrical panels and uninterruptible power supplies.

Adjacent Spaces: *Generic Rooms, Corridors, WCs:* Neighboring spaces influencing thermal exchanges without being part of the main cooling system.

To enhance simulation accuracy, the supply and return plenums, racks, and hot aisles were modeled as separate geometric zones. This allowed for detailed analysis of temperature, pressure, and airflow velocity differences within each zone. Construction materials were characterized using the IES VE database, supplemented by project data, to ensure realistic thermal modeling. Each element was defined based on its physical and thermal properties, such as the Hot Aisle Containment System, which minimizes hot and cold air mixing to maximize heat recovery efficiency.

4.2 Use Profiles

Project profiles are essential tools for defining operational schedules and thermal settings for HVAC systems and internal loads across various zones. These profiles, configured within the APpro module, enable precise control over system on/off schedules, temperature setpoints, setback values, and operational patterns. By tailoring these profiles to match specific space needs, the simulation accurately reflects energy consumption and environmental conditions.

Adjacent Spaces (Offices and Auxiliary Rooms):

Operating Hours: HVAC systems operate from 8:00 AM to 6:00 PM, with setbacks during off-peak hours.

Temperature Setpoints and Setbacks:

Heating: 20 °C during operation, 15 °C during unoccupied periods.

Cooling: 24 °C during operation, 30 °C during unoccupied periods.

Load Profiles: Internal gains from lighting, equipment, and occupancy align with typical office schedules, reflecting realistic energy use patterns.

Server Room:

Temperature Control: Maintained within the ASHRAE-recommended range of 18 °C to 27 °C to ensure equipment reliability and flexibility for cooling capacities.

Humidity Control: Relative humidity is kept between 20% and 80%, with continuous HVAC operation to prevent hotspots and maintain uniform conditions.

IT Equipment Load: Modeled as a constant heat source using measured power consumption data to capture steady-state thermal behavior accurately.

By implementing these tailored profiles, the model accurately reflects distinct operational patterns and thermal requirements of each zone. For adjacent spaces, energy consumption is minimized during unoccupied hours, aligning with efficiency practices. In the server room, continuous HVAC operation ensures critical temperature and humidity thresholds are maintained, safeguarding IT equipment functionality. Figure 4 illustrates a temperature simulation over a year, demonstrating the robust foundation for simulating energy performance and environmental conditions.

Fig. 4. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Hot Aisle Containment Temperature Distribution, March typical day trend of temperature in the Server Room

4.3 Thermal Modeling

The configuration of thermal templates in IES VE was crucial for accurately capturing the distinct thermal characteristics of each zone within the data center. By assigning standardized thermal properties across zones, thermal templates enable consistent and flexible management of parameters, ensuring that the model accurately reflects variations in thermal behavior while maintaining computational efficiency. Each zone was specifically configured to reflect its unique thermal attributes, including internal heat gains, airflow rates, and boundary conditions. Real-time operational data from sensors installed throughout the data center provided a robust basis for calibrating the model.

This data included power consumption, rack-level temperatures, and humidity levels, allowing the model to closely align with observed conditions and enhance its predictive accuracy.

4.4 Integration of Electrical Systems

Linked to thermal management are electrical systems. The final PuE KPI is directly connected with electrical performance. So thermal management is helping to describe the losses of the system. Due to the sampling time frame (5 or 10 min), electrical representation of components must be done following a phasor representation (or DQ representation). A common application is in the steady-state analysis of an electrical network powered by time varying current where all signals are assumed to be sinusoidal with a common frequency. Phasor representation allows the analyst to represent the amplitude and phase of the signal using a single complex number. A simple simulation model for real time can be implemented, using some of the monitored variables as input and calculating the rest of monitoring pack. The comparison of these values in each time step can provide information of consistency of power meters values and a nominal exploitation of the data center, detecting any deviation. This logic is reflected in the electrical model illustrated in Fig. 5, which shows the representation of the data center's power feed and its integration into the simulation workflow.

Fig. 5. Electrical model of data center feed.

In a similar way, integration of other systems is possible. For example, new cooling machines of small components of the data center. These partial systems can be modelled independently and can be run in separate services. Integration times must be inside the sampling time frame and result may be integrated with monitoring signals, whether as redundant information to detect faults or as extra monitoring or KPIs information. An example of this modular modeling is provided in Fig. 6, which shows the chiller system representation integrated into the DT for detailed thermal behavior simulation.

Fig. 6. Chiller model

5 Discussion and Conclusions

The development of a digital twin for the High-Performance Computing for Artificial Intelligence (HPC4AI) facility at the University of Turin represents a groundbreaking approach to energy management in data centers. This initiative involves integrating a sophisticated monitoring system with a digital model that enables energy simulation and validation against real-world data. By capturing critical performance metrics, the system facilitates real-time analysis and decision-making, ensuring the reliability of the digital model through iterative validation. This process enhances operational efficiency and lays the foundation for comprehensive lifecycle management of the data center. The digital twin will enable proactive identification of inefficiencies, predictive maintenance, and strategic planning for future expansions, thereby reducing operational costs and environmental impact. By simulating various scenarios, stakeholders can assess the implications of design choices on energy consumption and performance, aligning operations with sustainability goals. This approach marks a significant shift from reactive to proactive energy management, addressing potential issues before they escalate. As the digital twin is refined, it is expected to become a valuable tool for optimizing energy use throughout the data center’s lifecycle, contributing to more sustainable practices in high-performance computing environments.

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